

SCIENTIFIC, ARTISTIC CREATIVITY AND CREATIVITY OF FAITH IN THE UNLIMITED POSSIBILITIES OF CONSCIOUSNESS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13292427>

Annotation: This article examines the artistic, scientific and creative work of faith. The author reveals the content of understanding of creativity and the ways to achieve it in the scientific and artistic forms of creativity and their awareness. The concepts of the absolute spirit, the connection between freedom and spirit are considered. The main thing in the creative process is to be in the action of creativity at every subsequent moment of life. All other human actions must come from this creative action. If we take away the state of the creative process from consciousness, then a person cannot meet the requirements that are presented to a person. Any interest in a person's consciousness must be turned into creative creativity.

Key words: creativity, arts, philosophy, scientific and creative, absolute spirit, scientific and artistic forms.

1 INTRODUCTION

"When you read ancient history, it seems that you find yourself in another world, with other creatures... However, these people existed, and they were human beings similar to us. What prevents us from being like them? Our prejudices, our base philosophy, petty selfish passions, united in all hearts with egoism as a result of our absurd institutions, which it was not genius that brought to life," Jean-Jacques Rousseau admits in his philosophical revelation.

2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

He genius that brings to life wise people not only of antiquity, but also wise people of all times and peoples, is a creative process. The creative process is a property of human consciousness, which is the main property in relation to all other properties of consciousness. The creative process is the basis of all human actions. For this reason, the creative process is not an act of consciousness, but an action.

What a person is in his own consciousness is what he is at this moment in his life. The main thing in the creative process is to be in the action of creativity at every subsequent moment of life. All other human actions must come from this creative action. If we take away the state of the creative process from consciousness, then a person cannot meet the requirements that are presented to a person. Any interest in a person's consciousness must be turned into creative creativity. Creativity is impossible within the limits of the subject-object relations of sensory perception, since staying at the level of "I - eat", where the infinity of consciousness is subordinate to the finite body, any creativity is impossible.

For my philosophical path, it is important to note that I do not believe in the possibility of rational ontology, I believe only in the possibility of a phenomenology of spiritual experience, symbolically described. Creativity for me is not so much a design in the final, creative product, but rather a revelation of the infinite, a flight to infinity, not objectification, but transcending".

3 ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE ON THE SUBJECT

In the most general form, it is necessary to divide the creative process into three types:

1. Scientific creativity;
2. Artistic creativity;
3. Creativity of faith.

All these three types ultimately lead to the same phenomenon, which can be called the path of advancement through the stages of perfection of one's consciousness, which opens up its unlimited possibilities. The unlimited possibilities of consciousness open up an idea that is a product of its essence - the spirit. The spirit is the source of human existence, of all levels of consciousness, and at the same time the discovery of the spirit is discovery of the cause of all existence.

At this level, absolute creativity is possible, which can materialize in scientific work, artistic creativity, because of intimate experience in faith. The results of scientific creativity violate the traditionally established boundaries of not only the humanities, but also the natural sciences. However, until now, a scientist who is in scientific creativity must have the power of the spirit of his own consciousness in order to be able to defend the ideas revealed to him as a result of this creativity.

The essence of scientific creativity is to overcome the established, but no one will envy the life of a scientist who dares to encroach on the established and become traditional. Artistic creativity completely frees a person from the problems that accompany a creative scientist and that make him different from the majority. The results of artistic creativity are ideas that are accepted not only by representatives of artistic creativity, but by all of humanity. The ideas of artistic creativity are very similar to the ideas of fairy tales, which are accepted by all humanity without exception. In fiction and fairy tales, humanity sees his hopes and dreams for the future. However, in artistic creativity it is necessary to see the highest reality of the consciousness of a person who is in a creative search. Artistic creativity includes all types of creativity where there is

an idea that is beyond space and time, but which strives for materialization. For example, a painting painted by an artist is the materialization of an idea that the artist is looking for in the creative process. This search can continue for a very long time, but as soon as the discovery of the idea takes place, the idea materializes.

To materialize the next idea, the artist needs to enter a new creative search process. Even if the artist returns to the previous idea, he will lack the creative search in which he was. For this reason, he will lose those subtle experiences in the state of his consciousness in which he was in the search for ignorance, in the process of searching.

In any creativity, the search process itself is important, and not the result of this search. Creativity is the presence of consciousness in the present. The present prepares for the future. In the present, the future is revealed not only of the person himself, but of all humanity. In the present, the future end of existence is revealed, but not the essence of the creator. In creativity there is only the present, since the past no longer exists and the future has not yet arrived. The absolute search is a search in faith. Scientific creativity and artistic creativity are like two peas in a pod, similar to each other. Both in scientific creativity and in artistic creativity, a person has the action of searching for consciousness of what has not yet been revealed to him.

However, if in scientific and artistic creativity the intermediate goals of discovering ideas that are not at the highest level of generalization are set, then in faith there is hope of discovering an absolute idea. In the discovery of an absolute idea, that is, in faith, human consciousness does not need to materialize its ideas in the form of scientific works or the results of artistic creativity. In true faith, the discovery of an idea exists in order to use its power to discover an idea of a greater level of generalization. In faith, this must happen until the absolute idea is revealed to consciousness, which must disappear so that the spirit, as the source of the idea, can remain. The presence of the spirit is self-contemplation of absolute truth, which exists at that absolute peak where nothing else can exist. "It is one thing to know the truth and another thing to communicate it to others; just as everyone enthusiastically worships the first, so few practice the second as it should be done. While recognizing truth as more valuable than prosperity and honor, most people at the same time without hesitation prefer the latter. And this happens not only because they, parting with the comprehension of the truth or timidly following it; they want to use the acquired wealth and titles, but because of a pathetic and unscrupulous admiration for those in power, and at the same time an indifferent and contemptuous attitude towards scientists." The absolute idea opens an understanding of the essence of being, and the spirit of consciousness is able to dwell in the essence of being directly. In other words, the spirit of consciousness returns consciousness, like the prodigal son, to God. "To understand my thoughts," writes N. Berdyaev, "it is very important to understand that for

me, human creativity is not a requirement of man and his right but is a requirement of God from man and a duty of man. God expects a creative act from man, as man's response to God's creative act. The same is true about human creativity as it is about human freedom. Human freedom is God's requirement from man, man's duty to attitude towards him... Man waits for the birth of God in him. God is waiting for man to be born in Him. It is at this depth that the question of creativity must be posed."

4 ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

An idea, not materialized either in linguistic forms, or in scientific works, or in the results of artistic creativity, resides in the element of its own existence, as an absolute idea, as the spirit of consciousness and God, as the essence of being. The ability to materialize an idea is at the lower levels of consciousness. To fall below what we ca

ll being in an idea is the loss of this state of consciousness. In his place the pattern of the possibility of materializing an idea comes into play.

The absolute completeness of the idea is lost in the final form of materialization. In an absolute, non-materialized idea, consciousness is in absolute freedom, but in a materialized idea, this freedom is lost. The discovery of this idea by Salvador Dali results in the judgment of his maximalism: "Everything that is poured into form is ugly... Freedom, if we define it as an aesthetic category, is an organic inability to take shape, amorphism itself. And form is a special reaction of matter subjected to pressure. And the more perfect this matter is, the more chances it must die, while imperfect species adapt, use all the opportunities left to them, shimmer, fill all the niches, thereby resisting oppression in their own way and ultimately acquiring a form, their own unique appearance."

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The state of consciousness in creative search is the fourth dimension, which is most often spoken about by representatives of natural and scientific knowledge. However, the fourth dimension is the main subject of humanitarian knowledge. This path is an action that reveals the idea, spirit, essence of being, absolute freedom, absolute goodness, absolute beauty and absolute truth. Spirit as the essence of consciousness and absolute the essence of being is the ultimate limit of creative search, which opens endless infinity.

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